

COMMON RISK FACTORS FOR ECTOPIC PREGNANCY IN YOUNG ADULTS: CLINIC-BASED CASE CONTROL STUDY

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Background: Ectopic pregnancy is a severe health problem for women of childbearing age. It is hypothesized that the main risk factors for EP are conditions or procedures, which can result in tubal damage [1,2].

Objective. We aimed to study the potential risk factors for the development of ectopic pregnancy in young adults.

Materials and methods. We conducted a retrospective case-control study to investigate the role of several risk factors in ectopic pregnancy based on the clinical database of patients in the 1st Clinic of Samarkand State Medical Institute. To a total of 152 cases, 304 controls were matched according to social and demographic characteristics, history of smoking, surgical, obstetric and gynaecological history. There also, information about assisted conception and contraceptive use were collected.

Results. The mean age of cases was 25.4 ± 6.2 . The majority of patients were under 30 years of age. The identified risk factors for the development of ectopic pregnancy were a history of the previous ectopic pregnancy (adjusted odds ratio (OR= 9.2, 95% CI 3.2-16.7) and a history of pelvic inflammatory diseases (OR=4.2, 95% CI 1.82-7.33). Other risk factors associated with an increased risk of ectopic pregnancy history of miscarriages or abortions (OR= 2.6, 95% CI 1.01-4.82), infertility problems (OR=1.9, 95% CI 0.91-3.12), the use of artificial conception tools (OR=3.9, 95% CI 1.56-5,67), previous or current use of the intrauterine device (OR= 3.01, 95% CI 1.67-5,91), previously performed caesarean section (OR=2.9, 95% CI 1.02-6.21) and regular smoking (OR = 2.03, 95% CI 0.98-5,44).

Conclusions: Increased awareness of risk factors allows early and accurate diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy. This study showed that previous pelvic inflammatory diseases is a major etiological factor in ectopic pregnancy. In addition, other factors associated with ectopic pregnancy, such as an earlier ectopic pregnancy, a history of infertility and an induced conception cycle, may result from a previous pelvic infection, which can lead to tubal complications. We recommend considering these factors as potential targets for future interventions.

References:

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